

SOME CHALLENGES AND DIFFERENT WAYS OF DEVELOPING DISCOURSE AMONG FIRST-GRADE PUPILS

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Abstract English has become the most widely spoken language in the world and has achieved significant status in most countries, including Uzbekistan. Discourse English is vital for first-grade pupils in Uzbekistan because it lays a foundation for their academic and career success, and opens up the possibilities for cross-cultural understanding and accelerated learning. This article spotlights some challenges in developing verbal communication among first-grade learners and some useful ways to grow their oral communication.

Keywords: discourse, communication, CLIL, curricula, first-grade learners, challenges, vocabulary.

The status of English in Uzbekistan has grown significantly over the past few years. The government of Uzbekistan has made it a priority to develop the English language skills of its people, recognizing the benefits gained from its global status. The English language is highly important in Uzbekistan as it provides opportunities for its citizens to enhance their international communication skills, increase employment and trade opportunities, and improve cross-cultural relationships. With the government's prioritized measures to develop and promote English language proficiency, Uzbekistan is rapidly progressing toward becoming proficient in the international language.

A renewal model of FLT (2013) in Uzbekistan was adapted to the CEFR standard (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning. Teaching. Assessment), this specifies the creation of new curricula, syllabuses, and teaching materials under the Competence-based and action-based approaches. 1-4 grade learners obtain an A1 level of language proficiency.

Developing discourse among first-grade pupils is a key aspect of teaching English at school. However, teachers face some challenges during teaching them.

Young children have a limited attention span, and keeping them engaged in meaningful communication can be challenging. Their minds can wander during a conversation which can lead to a lack of focus and difficulties in maintaining a discussion. Another challenge is vocabulary. Young learners may have limited vocabulary skills, making it difficult to express their ideas and engage in meaningful discourse. It might be difficult to participate in conversations since they might not know the words to describe their ideas. Moreover, some learners have shyness and inhibition: Young learners may feel shy or intimidated about speaking with others and expressing themselves in a second language. This can lead to them being hesitant about participating in group discussions or speaking up to express their own ideas. While learning the language they see different cultural differences that is unlike their culture. Young learners may come from different backgrounds, having different norms and cultural practices. This can lead to challenges with understanding each other's perspectives as well as linguistic codes. Limited Exposure is another difficulty in teaching language. Young learners may have had limited exposure to English outside of the classroom, making it tough to be fluent and confident in their expression.

To overcome these challenges, teachers can incorporate strategies to allow children to feel safe and enjoy the process of communication. As young children engage in their early years of schooling, developing strong communication skills is essential for both academic and social success. Teaching English to first-grade pupils can be challenging, but there are several approaches to make the process easier and more effective. They are unable to write and make notes so they learn language in an oral way. Here are some tips on how to teach English to first-grade pupils:

1. Start with basics: Begin with teaching the basics such as the English alphabet, numbers, and common vocabulary words. It is important to make sure the

instruction is age-appropriate, simple, and easy to understand, and use toys, flashcards, or songs to help first-year learners.

2. Use visuals: Use colorful and engaging visuals such as pictures, flashcards, and videos to reinforce the lesson's content, grab their attention, and make the learning process fun.

3. Introduce songs and rhymes: Singing songs and reciting rhymes is an excellent way to introduce new vocabulary and improve pronunciation while making the learning experience enjoyable and interactive.

4. Incorporate games and activities: Games and activities that include physical movement and are interactive can help engage children in the learning process while improving their memory retention.

5. Encourage verbal communication: Encourage seven-year-old students to practice speaking English both in and outside of the classroom. Reward and praise them for speaking English in a positive and supportive manner.

6. Use repetition: Repetition is an effective way to reinforce language structures and vocabulary. Repetitive exercises and drills can help students gain confidence while also improving their retention.

7. Teach grammar: Introduce simple grammar rules such as plural nouns, present tense, and conjunctions in an easy-to-understand way. Use fun and age-appropriate activities like sentence building and storytelling to practice grammar concepts.

8. Make it fun and engaging: Learning English should be fun and engaging for seven-year-old students. Use a variety of strategies such as songs, games, and storytelling to engage children's interests and create an exciting learning environment that motivates them.

9. Interactive Storytelling: Storytelling is an excellent way to develop early language skills. Engage children with interactive storytelling by pausing at intervals throughout the story to ask questions, and encouraging the children to participate in completing the story.

10. Show and Tell: First graders benefit greatly from show and tell. Encouraging them to share and present items they've brought from home lays the foundation for public speaking and communication skills.

11. Puppet Shows: Puppet shows can be an engaging and interactive way to develop discourse among first-grade pupils. Children can either watch or participate in the show, promoting language acquisition, story recall, and interaction.

12. Group Work: Group work is another way of developing discourse, where pupils can learn from their fellow pupils and communicate their ideas with them. Through activities like drawing, writing, and role play, children learn to express themselves and collaborate with their peers.

In Uzbekistan, schoolchildren learn from Guess What by Cambridge University Press which has carefully selected each theme for learners. This includes very interesting and vital themes and each topic highlights pupils' speaking skills. Each topic consists of vocabulary, grammar, story value, talk time, animal sounds and CLIL

For instance:

Topic: School

In the vocabulary part, pupils learn words related to school objects such as board, book, chair, desk, door, eraser, pen, pencil case, and window.

In the grammar part, they learn to count them using How many (chairs) can you see?

In the story value and talk time part, learners make up simple sentences with the words that they have learned during the topic.

In the animal sound part, they repeat sounds.

Each topic has CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) that has integrated other subjects such as art, science, geography, and math.

The precise book mostly emphasizes pupils' oral communication.

In conclusion, these are just a few of the many ways to develop discourses among first-grade pupils. Ultimately, creating a safe and engaging environment that encourages communication, creativity, and critical thinking is essential to foster effective communication skills in the early years of school. With patience, nurturing, and fun learning opportunities, first graders can develop a foundation of highly successful communication skills that will help them throughout their academic and future personal success. Teaching English to 7-year-old students requires patience, creativity, and an interactive approach. By using age-appropriate materials, visuals, songs, games, and activities, teachers can create an exciting and enjoyable learning environment that will help seven-year-old students develop their English language skills and make progress toward fluency.

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